

Financial Information Sources, Trust, and the Ostrich Effect: Evidence from Chinese Stock Investors during a Market Crisis

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January 31, 2026

[Original working draft v1 / Un-peer-reviewed]

“[...] intelligence birds must keep the information simple. Throw away anything that sounds too complicated. Only keep what is simple to grasp. Keep whatever news that seems friendly to the ears. If the information appears fuzzy and causes the brain to implode after two sentences, toss it away and stop listening. Doing so will make the news as orderly and simple to understand as the truth!”

—In “GHG Emissions,” *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

Abstract

Periods of market crisis are often accompanied by heightened fear and information overload, which can induce information avoidance behaviors such as the ostrich effect. While prior research has documented investors' tendency to avoid unfavorable information, little is known about how different information sources—and trust in those sources—jointly shape such behavior under extreme uncertainty. Drawing on Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) and employing Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics, this study examines how investors' regular securities-related information sources is associated with the ostrich effect during the 2022 market downturn in China, and how these associations are conditioned by trust. Using survey data from 1,451 Chinese individual stock investors, we model investors' recalled frequency of temporarily disengaging from stock investing as an indicator of information avoidance. The results show that regularly consulting professional sources, financial newspapers, and online forums is associated with information avoidance, whereas reliance on personal relationships and company disclosures is not. Importantly, trust moderates these relationships in distinct ways. Higher trust in professional sources is associated with reduced information avoidance, while higher trust in financial newspapers and online forums amplifies avoidance behavior. Among all sources, the interaction between trust and information referral is strongest for financial newspapers. These findings suggest that trust does not uniformly mitigate fear-driven avoidance. Instead, when combined with high-entropy information sources, trust can exacerbate cognitive and emotional strain, increasing investors' propensity to disengage. By highlighting the joint roles of informational entropy and trust, this study advances behavioral finance research and offers practical insights for investors, policymakers, and regulators seeking to improve decision-making resilience during periods of market crisis.

Keywords: Knowledge management; stock market investment; investment literacy; gains and losses; information space; rationality; fear; ostrich effect

Introduction

The historical evolution of financial markets reveals recurring episodes of extreme volatility and seemingly irrational behavior, posing persistent challenges to the assumption of perfect rationality embedded in traditional financial models. These challenges have become even more pronounced in the contemporary era of rapid digitalization, where real-time data flows, algorithmic trading, and AI-assisted decision-support systems increasingly shape market dynamics. Over recent decades, a growing body of research has documented the limitations of the Efficient Market Hypothesis, demonstrating that investor behavior does not merely follow optimization logic but is also shaped by systematic psychological biases operating under conditions of information asymmetry and abundance as well as cognitive overload. Rather than eliminating irrationality, the proliferation of digital

information and AI-enabled tools often amplifies it by accelerating decision cycles, increasing attentional competition, and fostering greater reliance on heuristics.

These cognitive biases, “the ones that skew our assessments away from an objective perception of information” (Johnson, Blumstein, Fowler, & Haselton, 2013), influence how individuals frame decision problems (Tversky & Kahneman, 1981), misjudge the probabilities of events (Lichtenstein, Fischhoff, & Phillips, 1982), and experience post-decisional regret (R. G. Clarke, Krase, & Statman, 1994), thereby further distancing investment decision-making from reality (Soprano et al., 2024). For example, investors frequently exhibit overconfidence, leading to excessive trading and persistent misjudgment of their own abilities (Barber & Odean, 2001; Daniel & Hirshleifer, 2015; Gervais & Odean, 2001; Slovic, Fischhoff, & Lichtenstein, 1980). In addition, the rapid dissemination of news and algorithmically curated signals can intensify overreactions and misinterpretations of new information, causing asset prices to deviate from their fundamental values in the short run (J. Clarke, Chen, Du, & Hu, 2020; De Bondt & Thaler, 1985; Weller, 2018). Loss aversion further induces investors to hold losing positions for too long while realizing gains too early (Kahneman & Tversky, 2013; Odean, 1998; Shefrin & Statman, 1985). Moreover, herding behavior is increasingly magnified in digitally networked markets, particularly during periods of heightened uncertainty and extreme market conditions (Huberman & Regev, 2001; Kyriazis, 2020; Nilsson & Backman, 2024). Collectively, these findings laid the foundation for behavioral finance and demonstrate that financial markets do not merely reflect information itself, but also the cognitively bounded ways in which individuals perceive, interpret, and respond to that information.

Among these cognitive biases, a notable phenomenon in financial decision-making is information avoidance, whereby individuals deliberately refrain from acquiring information even when it is freely available and potentially beneficial (Golman, Hagmann, & Loewenstein, 2017). The ostrich effect—a term introduced by Galai and Sade (2006)—captures this tendency to ignore or avoid unfavorable information, including feedback that is critical for accurately assessing risks and goal progress. Rather than confronting adverse signals proactively, individuals often engage in avoidance behaviors, metaphorically akin to an ostrich burying its head in the sand. Building on this concept, Karlsson, Loewenstein, and Seppi (2009) provided empirical evidence of the ostrich effect among individual investors in the Swedish and U.S. stock markets, showing that investors are more inclined to seek information during favorable market conditions while systematically avoiding it when faced with neutral or negative signals.

Irrational patterns in information processing and decision-making often stem from fundamental psychological states such as fear, greed, and instinctive emotional responses (Lo, Repin, & Steenbarger, 2005). In the case of the ostrich effect, information avoidance is commonly motivated by a fear-driven response, whereby individuals deliberately evade information that may be psychologically threatening, demotivating, or costly to confront (Golman et al., 2017). Such avoidance may also arise from concerns about negative self-assessment, projection biases regarding future outcomes, or an implicit abdication of responsibility when facing unfavorable feedback. From an evolutionary psychological perspective, fear-driven biases may have developed as adaptive mechanisms to minimize

the long-term costs of decision errors in complex environments under cognitive and evolutionary constraints (Johnson et al., 2013). These fear-based responses tend to become particularly salient during periods of crisis, when uncertainty and perceived threat intensify.

In particular, during the COVID-19 pandemic, fear is an adaptive emotion that serves to protect the organism from potential danger, despite some of its negative consequences (Mertens, Lodder, Smeets, & Duijndam, 2023). While excessive or chronic fear is associated with heightened anxiety, stress, and depression (Fitzpatrick, Harris, & Drawve, 2020; Lee, Jobe, Mathis, & Gibbons, 2020; Montano & Acebes, 2020), it has also been shown to promote preventive behaviors in the context of COVID-19, such as hand washing and social distancing, thereby contributing to the reduction of virus transmission (Harper, Satchell, Fido, Latzman, & addiction, 2021). At the same time, accumulating evidence indicates that heightened psychological distress may foster information avoidance, manifesting in ostrich-like behaviors that subsequently undermine compliance with preventive measures (Siebenhaar, Köther, & Alpers, 2020).

Analogous mechanisms are likely to operate in financial markets, where exposure to persistent losses or unfavorable market signals can impose substantial emotional costs, motivating investors to temporarily disengage from information acquisition and decision-making (Li, 2023). Despite the relevance of this mechanism, empirical investigations of the ostrich effect among stock investors during the COVID-19 pandemic remain absent. Scholars further suggest that access to high-quality information sources and trust in those sources play a crucial role in mitigating information avoidance (Gisoni et al., 2022; Li, 2023). Accordingly, analyzing how different information channels are associated with investors' avoidance behaviors—and how these effects are conditioned by trust—constitutes a promising direction for advancing behavioral finance research in the context of pandemic-induced market disruptions. Such insights are particularly salient given projections that the annual likelihood of extreme epidemic events may increase up to threefold in the coming decades (Marani, Katul, Pan, & Parolari, 2021).

As the world's second-largest equity market, China occupies a pivotal position in global financial stability, making an understanding of Chinese stock investors' behavior during crises particularly valuable for informing adaptive policy design and market-stabilization strategies. In 2022, the Chinese stock market experienced a pronounced and prolonged downturn amid elevated uncertainty. Both the Shanghai Stock Exchange Composite Index and the Hang Seng Index declined by more than 13% during the year (Q.ai, 2022; Trading Economics, 2026). This sustained downturn was driven by a combination of stringent COVID-19 containment measures—most notably large-scale lockdowns such as that in Shanghai—which severely disrupted production networks and supply chains, generating widespread negative abnormal returns across firms and their upstream and downstream partners. These economic shocks were further compounded by heightened political and policy uncertainty later in the year, as the continued commitment to the zero-COVID strategy triggered sharp sell-offs, particularly in technology and private-sector stocks, reinforcing market-wide fear and uncertainty (Q.ai, 2022; Song, Lee, & Koo, 2025). Collectively, these conditions render 2022 a quasi-natural experiment for investigating fear-

driven information avoidance behaviors under extreme uncertainty. Moreover, as China represents a large non-Western market with distinct institutional and cultural characteristics—and remains relatively underrepresented in behavioral finance research—evidence from this context offers valuable comparative insights for future cross-cultural studies, particularly in relation to Western financial markets.

Based on these considerations, the present study pursues two main objectives. First, it examines how the information sources investors rely on for investment decisions are associated with the ostrich effect, operationalized as the self-reported frequency with which investors temporarily stopped investing in stocks during the 2022 crisis. Second, it investigates how these associations vary as a function of investors' trust in different information sources.

In order to complete these objectives, the study adopts Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) as its theoretical foundation for model formulation, and employs Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics to analyze survey data from 1,451 Chinese individual investors (Vuong, La, & Nguyen, 2025; Vuong & Nguyen, 2024; Vuong, Nguyen, & La, 2022). GITT—an extension of Mindsponge Theory—is a socio-psychological information-processing framework grounded in insights from quantum mechanics and Shannon's information theory, enabling it to account for fear-induced behaviors that are dynamic, non-linear, and shaped by complex interactions among informational stimuli and moderating factors. By integrating GITT with Bayesian inference, this study aims to provide nuanced insights into how fear-driven information avoidance emerges in crisis contexts, thereby contributing to the design of strategies to mitigate investor fear and support the development of more resilient and sustainable financial markets.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

This study applies Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) to examine how different information sources are associated with stock investors' ostrich effects, and how these associations are conditional on investors' trust in those sources (Vuong, La, et al., 2025; Vuong & Nguyen, 2024). GITT extends the Mindsponge theory, which was developed referring to the latest evidence from neuroscience and evolutionary biology, by incorporating principles from information theory and quantum-inspired perspectives (Hertog, 2023; Rovelli, 2018; Shannon, 1948; Vuong, 2023). More broadly, it aligns with a long-standing tradition in the social sciences that draws on concepts from the physical sciences to explain economic behavior and human cognition. Classical economists such as Adam Smith were influenced by Newtonian mechanics, while later scholars—including Leon Walras in general equilibrium theory and Adolphe Quetelet in social physics—further advanced this interdisciplinary trajectory. This tradition continued into the twentieth century with innovations such as the Black–Scholes equation (Vuong, 2001).

Within GITT, three interrelated principles—granularity, relationality, and indeterminacy—jointly govern how information is processed and translated into behavior (Nguyen, Sari, et al., 2025). Granularity emphasizes that cognition operates on discrete informational units,

only a limited subset of which can be retained and reused due to finite cognitive resources. Relationality highlights that behavioral outcomes emerge from continuous interactions between newly encountered information and pre-existing cognitive structures such as beliefs, expectations, values, and prior experiences. Indeterminacy underscores the probabilistic and non-linear nature of these interactions, implying that information evaluation and preference formation are context-dependent rather than deterministic. Retaining the core principles of Mindsponge Theory, GITT further posits that information acceptance depends on perceived credibility and subjective cost–benefit assessments: information perceived as trustworthy, relevant, and low-cost is more likely to be integrated into the mindset, whereas information associated with high cognitive or emotional costs is more likely to be filtered out (Sari, Duong, Li, Nguyen, & Vuong, 2024; Vuong, 2018).

Grounded in GITT, this study conceptualizes each investor’s mind as an information collection–cum–processing system that continuously seeks to maintain a relatively low-entropy cognitive state. In this framework, cognitive entropy reflects the degree of uncertainty arising from multiple competing interpretations of market conditions, asset value, and future outcomes. Such entropy can be formally described using Shannon (1948)’s information entropy equation:

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i) \log_2 P(x_i)$$

where $H(X)$ denotes the informational entropy of an investor’s cognitive state X , and $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ represents a finite set of possible cognitive outcomes—such as alternative interpretations of market signals, assessments of portfolio performance, or expectations about future returns—each associated with a subjective probability $\{P(x_1), P(x_2), \dots, P(x_n)\}$. Within the context of financial decision-making, entropy increases as investors are exposed to large volumes of novel, contradictory, or emotionally charged information (e.g., market crashes, conflicting expert opinions, or sensational financial news). Such inputs expand the set of plausible cognitive outcomes and flatten the subjective probability distribution across them. Cognitive entropy reaches its maximum when all interpretations are perceived as equally likely, that is, when $P(x_i) = \frac{1}{n}$, reflecting a state in which the investor lacks a clear prioritization among competing beliefs, expectations, or courses of action.

When investors enter financial markets, they typically do so with expectations of positive returns and benefit maximization. Their internal information—comprising beliefs, past experiences, financial knowledge, and trusted market narratives—interacts to form a coherent, low-entropy cognitive representation in which the invested asset is perceived as valuable, comprehensible, and manageable. Even when investors anticipate potential losses, this internal system often reframes expectations toward cost minimization (e.g., believing that losses will be limited or temporary), thereby preserving cognitive coherence and emotional stability.

However, during crises—such as the COVID-19 pandemic—market shocks can severely disrupt this internally constructed low-entropy state by injecting large volumes of high-

entropy information, including sharp price declines, contradictory expert opinions, socially reinforced emotional messages, and alarming media narratives. These informational shocks simultaneously undermine both benefit-maximization and cost-minimization expectations, sharply increasing cognitive uncertainty and emotional strain.

When confronted with abrupt spikes in cognitive entropy, investors may adopt different entropy-regulation strategies. Some investors attempt to reorganize their internal information structure by actively seeking clarification, cross-checking sources, or updating beliefs in light of new evidence. This strategy also reflects an effort to restore a lower-entropy state through the selective integration of credible informational units. Others respond by reducing informational exposure—disengaging from news, avoiding portfolio monitoring, or delaying information acquisition altogether. This deliberate contraction of information inflow constitutes an informational withdrawal and manifests behaviorally as the ostrich effect. In more extreme cases, investors may engage in panic selling, which represents an entropy-elimination strategy that removes the uncertainty-generating asset itself, thereby collapsing the informational state space associated with future outcomes. From this perspective, fear-related behaviors—specifically information avoidance—can be understood as an emergent outcome of the mind’s information-processing dynamics under crisis conditions.

Although fear has been defined in multiple ways, there is broad agreement that it involves both informational antecedents—signals indicating potential threat—and observable behavioral consequences (Mobbs et al., 2019). These antecedents may originate externally, such as through negative market news or alarming expert commentary, or internally, such as anticipated losses inferred from memory, past experiences, and prior belief structures (Adolphs, 2013; Vlaeyen, Crombez, & Linton, 2016). According to GITT, the information structure preexisting in the mind functions as a buffering system that moderates how new, disruptive signals are processed. This internal structure—comprising accumulated knowledge, beliefs, experiences, and values—shapes whether incoming information amplifies cognitive entropy or can be absorbed and reorganized at manageable cognitive and emotional cost.

When this internal information system is coherent, well-calibrated, and aligned with objective market realities, it enables investors to concentrate subjective probability mass on a narrower set of plausible interpretations, thereby constraining entropy hike. Conversely, when the internal system is fragmented, weakly grounded, or internally inconsistent, new information diffuses probability mass across many competing interpretations, accelerating entropy escalation and increasing psychological strain.

Within this process, information sources and trust play pivotal regulatory roles. Information sources differ systematically in informational quality, credibility, and noise. High-quality sources—such as regulated disclosures or well-established expert analyses—tend to provide inputs that are more consistent with objective reality and therefore easier to integrate into existing cognitive structures (Nguyen, 2025). In contrast, low-quality or sensationalized sources may introduce ambiguous, emotionally charged, or inaccurate signals that are poorly aligned with reality, particularly during crises. As a result, investors

relying on different information sources may experience markedly different entropy trajectories when facing identical market shocks, leading to heterogeneous patterns of information avoidance. Based on this reasoning, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Investors regularly referring to different information sources exhibit different levels of information avoidance during crisis periods.

Meanwhile, trust evaluation operates as a cognitive gatekeeping mechanism that governs the filtering and integration of incoming information and functions as an energy-saving process by allowing individuals to prioritize reliable inputs and limit unnecessary entropy accumulation within the mind (Nguyen, Duong, et al., 2025; Santirocchi, Spataro, Alessi, Rossi-Arnaud, & Cestari, 2023; Tanemura, Kakizaki, Kusumi, Onodera, & Chiba, 2022). Information originating from highly trusted sources is more likely to be absorbed into the mindset and assigned greater cognitive weight, thereby exerting stronger influence on investors' information processing and behavioral responses. In contrast, information from low-trust sources is less likely to be absorbed or is processed only superficially, which attenuates its impact on cognitive evaluations and subsequent behavior. In this sense, trust conditions the extent to which information from different sources is associated with investors' propensity to engage in information avoidance.

H2: The associations between information sources and information avoidance are conditional on investors' trust in those sources.

In the following sections, we present the variable descriptions, model formulation, and methodological rationale used to examine these hypotheses.

Model Specification

Data and Variables

This study draws on a dataset comprising 1,451 Chinese individual stock investors who reported their fear responses and fear-regulation behaviors during the extremely volatile market conditions of 2022, along with a range of information- and knowledge-based factors (e.g., investment literacy) that may shape fear intensity and coping strategies (Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2025). The survey was administered between 25 April and 5 May 2023 to members of 10 WeChat stock trading groups, each consisting of approximately 128 to 497 members. These groups were formed through promotional activities by financial and stock market content creators on Douyin (the Chinese version of TikTok). In total, the combined membership across the 10 groups was 2,632 users. The questionnaire was created using the WeChat mini-application "Survey Star," and the survey link was shared directly within the WeChat groups. Prior to full deployment, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with five participants to ensure clarity, comprehensibility, and the absence of technical or interpretive errors.

A total of 1,525 respondents completed the online survey, yielding a response rate of 57.94%. All responses were anonymized and handled in accordance with relevant ethical standards and data protection regulations. The study protocol and survey design were

reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the China University of Political Science and Law, which confirmed that participants' rights, welfare, and well-being were fully protected.

Following data collection, survey responses were retrieved from Google Forms and WeChat's survey platform and merged into a single Microsoft Excel (xls) file. A data quality screening procedure was then conducted to identify and remove low-quality responses. Web-based surveys are particularly susceptible to response biases such as straightlining (providing identical responses across items using the same scale) and select-all behavior (selecting all options in multiple-choice questions), both of which can substantially distort analytical results. Consistent with established practice, responses exhibiting these behaviors were excluded from the dataset. After removing 74 low-quality responses, the final analytical sample consisted of 1,451 valid observations.

The questionnaire was designed based on Mindsponge Theory and existing evidence from the life sciences. Items measuring fear-related behaviors were developed by drawing on biological and psychological conceptualizations of fear and adapting them to the financial investment context. Other variables were constructed in accordance with the Mindsponge information-processing worldview. Accordingly, questionnaire items were organized into six conceptual categories reflecting different conceptual boundaries of the Mindsponge-based information process: (1) Environment, (2) Trust Evaluation, (3) Information Collection and Processing, (4) Mindset, (5) Outcomes, and (6) Socio-demographic Information.

In the present study, we employed one outcome variable and ten explanatory variables. The ostrich effect—conceptualized as information avoidance through temporary disengagement from stock investing—was operationalized using the variable *Fear_StopInvest*, derived from item *E1_3* in the original dataset. This item asked respondents: “During 2022, did you consider or take action to stop investing in stocks for a while and then come back?” Responses were recorded on three values: “No,” “Yes, a few times,” and “Yes, many times.” This variable belongs to the Outcome category.

Information sources regularly consulted for securities-related information were captured using five binary variables: *PersonalRelationships*, *ProInfluence*, *FinNewspapers*, *CompanySource*, and *OnlineForums*. Respondents were presented with a list of potential information sources and asked to select all that they regularly referred to. *PersonalRelationships* was coded as 1 if the respondent selected family members or close friends. *ProInfluence* was coded as 1 if the respondent selected investment advisory groups, consulting firms, or media experts. *CompanySource* was coded as 1 if the respondent selected corporate websites or companies' financial reports. *FinNewspapers* and *OnlineForums* were coded as 1 if the respondent selected financial newspapers or online investment forums, respectively. All information-source variables were derived from the Environment category.

Investors' trust in each information source was measured using variables from the Trust Evaluation category. Respondents rated their trust in each source on a four-point Likert scale, ranging from “completely distrust” to “completely trust.” *TrustPersonalRelationships* was constructed as the average trust score for information

obtained from family members and close friends. The remaining trust variables—*TrustProInfluence*, *TrustFinNewspapers*, *TrustCompanySource*, and *TrustOnlineForums*—correspond to the same five information sources described above. The variable description are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable Descriptions

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Values
<i>Fear_StopInvest</i>	Investor’s frequency of experiencing the ostrich effect during the 2022 market crash	Numerical	1 = No, 2 = Yes, a few times, 3 = Yes, many times
<i>PersonalRelationships</i>	Whether the investor regularly refer to either family members or friends for securities-related information	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>ProInfluence</i>	Whether the investor regularly refer to either securities investment groups, consulting firms, or media experts for securities-related information	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>FinNewspapers</i>	Whether the investor regularly refer to financial-specific newspaper for securities-related information	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>CompanySource</i>	Whether the investor regularly refer to either company’s financial statements or official websites for securities-related information	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No
<i>OnlineForums</i>	Whether the investor regularly refer to the online forum for	Binary	1 = Yes, 0 = No

	securities-related information		
<i>TrustPersonalRelationships</i>	Investor's level of trust toward information provided by family members and friends	Numerical	1= Completely distrust, 2= Slightly distrust, 3= Slightly trust, 4= Completely trust
<i>TrustProInfluence</i>	Investor's level of trust toward information provided by securities investment groups, consulting firms, and media experts	Numerical	1= Completely distrust, 2= Slightly distrust, 3= Slightly trust, 4= Completely trust
<i>TrustFinNewspapers</i>	Investor's level of trust toward information provided by financial-specific newspaper	Numerical	1= Completely distrust, 2= Slightly distrust, 3= Slightly trust, 4= Completely trust
<i>TrustCompanySource</i>	Investor's level of trust toward information provided by the company's financial statement and official website	Numerical	1= Completely distrust, 2= Slightly distrust, 3= Slightly trust, 4= Completely trust
<i>TrustOnlineForums</i>	Investor's level of trust toward information provided by online forums	Numerical	1= Completely distrust, 2= Slightly distrust, 3= Slightly trust, 4= Completely trust

Statistical Model

To test the proposed hypotheses regarding (i) the varying associations between investors' regularly consulted information sources and the ostrich effect, and (ii) the extent to which these associations are conditional on trust in those sources, we specify Model 1 as follows:

$$Fear_StopInvest \sim normal(\mu, \sigma) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 * PersonalRelationships_i + \beta_2 * ProInfluence_i + \beta_3 * FinNewspapers_i + \\ & \beta_4 * CompanySource_i + \beta_5 * OnlineForums_i + \beta_6 * PersonalRelationships_i * \\ & TrustPersonalRelationships_i + \beta_7 * ProInfluence_i * TrustProInfluence_i + \beta_8 * \\ & FinNewspapers_i * TrustFinNewspapers_i + \beta_9 * CompanySource_i * \\ & TrustCompanySource_i + \beta_{10} * OnlineForums_i * TrustOnlineForums_i \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\beta_i \sim normal(M, S) \quad (1.3)$$

In this specification, μ_i denotes the investor i 's recalled frequency of experiencing information avoidance behavior (the ostrich effect) during the crisis period. The coefficients $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ capture the marginal associations between reference to different information sources and information avoidance. The interaction terms $\beta_6 - \beta_{10}$ represent the moderating effects of trust, indicating how investors' trust in each information source conditions the corresponding association with the ostrich effect. All regression coefficients are assigned normal prior distributions with mean M and standard deviation S . The logical network of Model 1 is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Model 1's logical network

Analysis and Validation

This study employs the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) to examine how different financial information sources are associated with individual investors' information avoidance behavior (the ostrich effect) during periods of market crisis, and how these associations are moderated by investors' trust in those sources. The BMF integrates the theoretical reasoning of GITT with the inferential strengths of Bayesian statistical modeling, enabling a probabilistic examination of complex cognitive and behavioral relationships under uncertainty (Nguyen, La, Le, & Vuong, 2022; Vuong et al., 2022).

At the theoretical level, GITT conceptualizes cognitive and behavioral outcomes as probabilistically emerging from dynamic interactions between pre-existing cognitive structures—such as beliefs, experiences, and values—and incoming environmental information. This perspective is particularly suitable for studying fear-driven investment behaviors during crises, where information flows are abundant, contradictory, and emotionally charged. The probabilistic worldview of GITT aligns naturally with Bayesian inference, which treats parameters, uncertainty, and belief updating as probability distributions rather than fixed quantities (Gill, 2015). This alignment allows the analytical framework to remain consistent with the study’s core assumption that investors’ responses to information shocks are inherently uncertain, context-dependent, and non-linear.

Several methodological considerations motivated the choice of Bayesian analysis over conventional frequentist approaches. Traditional null hypothesis significance testing has been attributed for contributing to reproducibility problems in the social and behavioral sciences (Camerer et al., 2018; Open Science Collaboration, 2015). In particular, *p*-values are highly sensitive to sample size and are frequently misinterpreted as definitive indicators of truth rather than probabilistic measures of evidence (Halsey, Curran-Everett, Vowler, & Drummond, 2015). Moreover, the reliance on dichotomous significance thresholds (e.g., $p < 0.05$) obscures effect magnitude and uncertainty (Masson & Loftus, 2003). Murphy (2025)’s analysis of 599 articles published across 10 psychology journals shows that between 76% and 85% of articles published from 2009 to 2021 that reported nonsignificant results misinterpreted nonsignificance as evidence of no effect, highlighting a pervasive interpretive error arising from the misuse and misinterpretation of *p*-values (Murphy, Merz, Reimann, & Fernández, 2025).

Bayesian inference directly addresses these limitations by producing credible intervals, which quantify the probability that a parameter lies within a given range conditional on the observed data (Wagenmakers et al., 2018). Unlike frequentist confidence intervals, which refer to long-run properties of hypothetical repeated samples, credible intervals allow intuitive probabilistic statements about parameters themselves (van Zyl, 2018). This feature is useful for the present study, where the focus is on estimating the strength and uncertainty of associations between information sources, trust, and avoidance behavior rather than on binary hypothesis rejection.

Prior specification constitutes a critical component of Bayesian modeling. Given the exploratory nature of this study and the absence of strong prior empirical estimates for the magnitude of the relationships under investigation, uninformative (flat) priors were initially adopted to allow the data to play a dominant role in shaping posterior estimates (Diaconis & Ylvisaker, 1985). To assess robustness, sensitivity analyses were conducted using weakly informative priors, specified as normal distributions centered at zero with a standard deviation of 0.5. These priors reflect skeptical assumptions about large effect sizes while remaining sufficiently flexible to accommodate meaningful relationships if supported by the data. Beyond robustness checking, informative priors can also mitigate multicollinearity and stabilize parameter estimates by constraining the parameter space—an advantage in models involving multiple correlated predictors and interaction terms (Adepoju & Ojo, 2018; Jaya, Tantular, & Andriyana, 2019; Leamer, 1973). Consistency of

results across alternative prior specifications therefore provides evidence of both inferential robustness and model stability.

All models were implemented using the `bayesvl` package (version 1.0.0) in R (La & Vuong, 2025; Vuong & La, 2019). The package interfaces with the Stan probabilistic programming language and adopts a Bayesian-network–inspired workflow in which statistical models are represented as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs). A key advantage of `bayesvl` is its ability to automatically generate regression structures and corresponding Stan code from user-specified relationship trees, enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in Bayesian analysis. The current release employs Stan’s No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) to ensure efficient and reliable posterior estimation (La et al., 2022). Parameter estimation was conducted using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling with four chains, each run for 5,000 iterations, including a 2,000-iteration warm-up phase.

Model fit was assessed using Pareto-smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out (PSIS-LOO) cross-validation (Vehtari & Gabry, 2024; Vehtari, Gelman, Gabry, & computing, 2017), which evaluates a model’s out-of-sample predictive performance by estimating how well it predicts each observation when that observation is omitted during model fitting. The computed LOO statistic is presented below:

$$LOO = -2LPPD_{loo} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log \int p(y_i|\theta) p_{post(-i)}(\theta) d\theta$$

where $p(y_i|\theta)$ represents the posterior distribution estimated from the dataset with observation y_i removed. The PSIS procedure relies on Pareto k diagnostics to identify influential observations; k values below 0.5 indicate good model fit, while values above 0.7 suggest potential instability.

Following confirmation of adequate model fit, MCMC convergence was evaluated using a combination of statistical and graphical diagnostics. The effective sample size (n_{eff}) was used to assess the number of independent draws from the posterior distribution, with values exceeding 1,000 indicating sufficient sampling for reliable inference (McElreath, 2018). Convergence across chains was further examined using the Gelman–Rubin statistic ($Rhat$), where values approaching 1.0 indicate successful convergence (Brooks & Gelman, 1998). Visual inspection of trace plots confirmed adequate chain mixing and stationarity.

To support transparency and reproducibility, all datasets and analytical code associated with this study have been made publicly available via Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/18447660>.

Results

We first evaluated model fit using PSIS-LOO diagnostics by inspecting the distribution of Pareto k values, as shown in Figure 2. All estimated k values are below 0.5, indicating a good correspondence between the model and the observed data.

Figure 2: PSIS plot of Model 1 estimated using uninformative priors

The estimation results for Model 1 are reported in Table 1. Convergence diagnostics indicate satisfactory model performance: all effective sample sizes exceed 1,000 ($n_{eff} > 1,000$), and the Gelman–Rubin shrinkage factors equal 1 for all parameters ($Rhat = 1$). These diagnostics suggest adequate mixing of the Markov chains and support reliable interpretation of the posterior distributions. Consistently, the trace plots shown in Figure 3 display stable fluctuations around a common stationary distribution, providing further evidence of convergence.

Figure 3: Trace plots of Model 1 estimated using uninformative priors

Table 2: Estimation results of Model 1

Parameter	Uninformative priors				Informative priors			
	M	SD	n_{eff}	$Rhat$	M	SD	n_{eff}	$Rhat$
<i>Constant</i>	1.91	0.09	10258	1	1.91	0.09	9715	1
<i>PersonalRelationships</i>	0.02	0.11	7712	1	0.03	0.11	7219	1
<i>ProInfluence</i>	0.27	0.11	7771	1	0.25	0.11	7236	1
<i>FinNewspapers</i>	- 0.64	0.21	8243	1	- 0.53	0.20	9021	1
<i>CompanySource</i>	0.15	0.32	8832	1	0.09	0.27	8912	1
<i>OnlineForums</i>	- 0.24	0.15	8631	1	- 0.22	0.14	8753	1
<i>PersonalRelationships*</i>	0.00	0.03	7421	1	0.00	0.03	7121	1

<i>TrustPersonalRelationships</i>								
<i>ProInfluence*</i> <i>TrustProInfluence</i>	- 0.06	0.03	7429	1	- 0.06	0.03	7362	1
<i>FinNewspapers*</i> <i>TrustFinNewspapers</i>	0.23	0.07	8860	1	0.20	0.06	8630	1
<i>CompanySource*</i> <i>TrustCompanySource</i>	- 0.06	0.10	8013	1	- 0.04	0.08	8920	1
<i>OnlineForums*</i> <i>TrustOnlineForums</i>	0.07	0.05	8123	1	0.07	0.05	8933	1
*Note: <i>M</i> is Mean, <i>SD</i> is standard deviation, <i>n_eff</i> is effective sample size, and <i>Rhat</i> is the Gelman–Rubin statistic								

The posterior distributions of the regression coefficients in Table 3 indicate that regularly referring to securities-related information from professional sources ($M_{ProInfluence}=0.27$ and $S_{ProInfluence}=-0.06$), financial newspapers ($M_{FinNewspapers}=-0.64$ and $S_{FinNewspapers}=0.21$), and online forums ($M_{OnlineForums}=-0.24$ and $S_{OnlineForums}=0.07$) is associated with systematic differences in investors' information avoidance behavior. In contrast, regularly referring to information from personal relationships or company sources shows no reliable association.

The 90% Highest Posterior Density Intervals (HPDIs), depicted as thick blue lines in Figure 4, further support the robustness of these associations. The HPDI for *ProInfluence* lies entirely on the positive side of zero, whereas those for *FinNewspapers* and *OnlineForums* lie almost entirely on the negative side. Although a small portion of the HPDI for *FinNewspapers* extends marginally into the positive region, this segment is negligible. Overall, the posterior evidence indicates that the associations for these three information sources are highly reliable.

Regarding moderation effects, only trust in professional sources ($M_{ProInfluence*TrustProInfluence}=-0.06$ and $S_{ProInfluence*TrustProInfluence}=0.03$), financial newspapers ($M_{FinNewspapers*TrustFinNewspapers}=0.23$ and $S_{FinNewspapers*TrustFinNewspapers}=0.07$), and online forums ($M_{OnlineForums*TrustOnlineForums}=0.07$ and $S_{OnlineForums*TrustOnlineForums}=0.05$) meaningfully moderate the relationships between information sources and information avoidance. The corresponding 90% HPDIs in Figure 4 indicate high posterior reliability for all three interaction terms. Moreover, posterior estimates obtained using informative priors—reflecting prior skepticism toward these associations—are nearly identical to those

obtained using uninformative priors. This convergence suggests that the results are robust to prior specification and unlikely to be driven by multicollinearity.

Figure 4: Posterior distributions of Model 1 coefficients estimated using uninformative priors

To clarify how regular exposure to professional sources, financial newspapers, and online forums relates to information avoidance at varying levels of trust, we substitute the posterior mean estimates into Equation (1.2) to compute predicted frequencies of recalled information avoidance behavior. The resulting marginal effects are visualized in Figures 5A–5C.

Figure 5A shows that investors who regularly refer to professional sources but exhibit low trust in them are more likely to experience the ostrich effect than even those who do not consult professional sources at all. As trust increases, however, information avoidance declines and converges toward the level observed among non-users of professional sources. In contrast, Figures 5B and 5C reveal a different pattern for financial newspapers and online forums. Investors who regularly consult these sources but do not trust them are less likely to exhibit ostrich behavior than non-users. As trust increases, however, information avoidance rises and eventually exceeds that of non-users.

Comparing across Figures 5A–5C, the magnitude of change in ostrich behavior associated with shifts in both referral and trust is greatest for financial newspapers, followed by professional sources and online forums, suggesting a particularly strong interaction between trust and financial news consumption during crisis periods.

Figure 5: Investor’s recalled frequency of experiencing information avoidance behavior during the 2022 market crash. Charts A-C visualize the behavior behaviors in the scenarios the investor using solely information from professional sources, financial news paper, and online forums, respectively

Discussion

The current study employed the Granular Interaction Thinking Theory and Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics to analyze 1451 Chinese investors, providing one of the first empirical examination of how information sources and trust associated with the ostrich effects, i.e., information avoidance behaviors during the market crisis. We found that investors’ references to professional sources, financial newspapers, and online forum are associated with the ostrich effect, while those related to information from personal relationships and company’s information do not. Trust in professional sources, financial newspapers, and online forum are also discovered to differently moderate the associations between information sources and ostrich effects. These findings support both hypotheses: first, that investors who regularly rely on different information sources exhibit distinct levels of information avoidance during crisis periods; and second, that the associations between information sources and information avoidance are conditional on investors’ trust in those sources.

Although information obtained from professional sources, financial newspapers, and online forums is all associated with the ostrich effect, their associations—and especially their interactions with trust—exhibit markedly different patterns. Specifically, investors who regularly consult professional sources and place higher trust in the information provided by these sources tend to avoid information less frequently. In contrast, investors who regularly rely on financial newspapers and online forums and exhibit higher trust in these sources are more likely to engage in information avoidance behaviors.

These divergent patterns provide further empirical support for the GITT reasoning outlined above. From a GITT perspective, information originating from high-quality professional sources—such as securities investment groups, consulting firms, or expert-driven financial media—tends to be more structured, analytically grounded, and better aligned with objective market conditions. Repeated exposure to, and trust in, such information contributes to the formation of a more coherent and well-calibrated internal information system within the investor’s mind. This system exhibits higher internal consistency and stronger compatibility between newly incoming information and existing cognitive structures. Thus, it is more resilient to entropy shocks—such as sudden market downturns and crisis-induced uncertainty during the COVID-19 pandemic—because it can more effectively regulate informational disorder and emotional turbulence. Investors with such capability are less inclined to engage in ostrich-like avoidance behaviors when facing adverse market signals.

At the same time, the moderating role of trust in professional sources further illuminates the mindsponge mechanism underlying information processing. When investors frequently consult professional sources but do not trust them, the incoming high-quality information encounters resistance from preexisting belief structures, values, or heuristics within the mind. This incompatibility impedes smooth information absorption, generating internal friction and elevating cognitive entropy rather than reducing it. Under such conditions, the mind fails to integrate the information into a stable mental framework, making continued information exposure psychologically costly. To regulate this heightened entropy, investors can temporarily disengage from market information and decision-making more frequently—manifesting as stopping investment activities or avoiding news.

In contrast, information from financial newspapers and online forums is generally characterized by higher uncertainty, greater noise, and weaker alignment with objective market fundamentals. Such sources often include fragmented narratives, sensational framing, anecdotal experiences, or emotionally charged interpretations. When investors place high trust in these lower-quality information sources, the mindsponge mechanism allows a large volume of such information to be absorbed into the internal cognitive system. However, because this information is less coherent and less reality-consistent, its accumulation increases internal entropy and reduces the system’s capacity to withstand external shocks. During periods of market crisis—when uncertainty and informational load intensify—investors with these high-entropy cognitive states become more vulnerable to overload. Consequently, they are more likely to resort to ostrich-like behaviors, such as deliberately avoiding market information, as a compensatory strategy to reduce cognitive and emotional strain.

Notably, the magnitude of change in ostrich behavior associated with shifts in both information referral and trust is greatest for financial newspapers, followed by professional sources and online forums, indicating a particularly strong interaction between trust and financial news consumption during crisis periods. This pattern can be explained by the distinctive informational position that financial newspapers occupy within the investor information environment. Compared to professional sources, financial newspapers typically exhibit higher informational entropy: their content is updated more frequently,

closely follows short-term market movements, and places strong emphasis on breaking news, volatility, and uncertainty. These characteristics substantially increase the volume, velocity, and emotional salience of incoming information, especially during crises when adverse signals dominate the news cycle. At the same time, financial newspapers possess higher perceived credibility than online forums, as their content is produced by trained journalists or domain specialists operating within established editorial institutions.

This combination—high entropy coupled with non-trivial credibility—renders financial newspapers particularly influential in shaping investors' internal information-processing dynamics. When trust in financial news is high, investors are more likely to attend to and absorb these high-entropy information flows rather than discounting or filtering them out. Instead of stabilizing expectations, however, such exposure may intensify cognitive and emotional strain by continuously confronting investors with fragmented, rapidly changing, and often negative market signals, thereby amplifying information avoidance tendencies.

This interpretation is further supported by the asymmetry in observed behaviors. Investors who regularly refer to financial newspapers but distrust them are less likely to exhibit ostrich behavior than who do not use financial newspapers, suggesting that these individuals primarily use financial news for situational monitoring while relying on alternative, trusted sources for interpretation and decision-making. In contrast, investors who both refer to and trust financial newspapers exhibit ostrich behavior more frequently than those who do not rely on financial news at all, consistent with the view that trusted, high-entropy information—when used as a primary decision input—can overwhelm cognitive processing and trigger avoidance responses.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

This study's findings advance behavioral finance by demonstrating that the effects of information sources on fear-driven behavior are non-monotonic and conditional on trust, rather than uniformly stabilizing or destabilizing. By integrating GITT with the ostrich effect literature, the findings show that trust does not always mitigate information avoidance; instead, when combined with high-entropy information sources—such as financial newspapers—it can amplify cognitive strain and increase avoidance behavior. This suggests that improving decision-making under uncertainty requires not only trust, but also access to high-quality information.

More broadly, the results suggests that entropy regulation can be an important psychological mechanism underlying information avoidance. Financial newspapers occupy a distinctive intermediate position—exhibiting higher entropy than professional sources but higher credibility than online forums—making them highly potent in influencing investors' internal information-processing dynamics during crises. This insight enriches existing models of investor attention and information avoidance by explicitly accounting for the joint roles of informational entropy and trust.

For individual investors, the findings suggest that how information is used matters as much as where it comes from. Reliance on trusted financial news as a primary decision-making input during crises may inadvertently increase fear and disengagement, whereas using such news for situational awareness while relying on more structured or analytical sources for

interpretation may help regulate cognitive load. For policymakers and regulators, the results underscore the importance of information governance during crises. Rather than focusing solely on combating misinformation, regulatory efforts should also consider the psychological consequences of high-frequency, high-salience financial news. Enhancing the availability and visibility of synthesized, interpretive information—such as expert briefings or regulated analytical summaries—may help investors better cope with market shocks. Financial literacy programs should likewise emphasize strategies for managing information overload and trust calibration, not merely improving access to information or knowledge.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study relies on self-reported, retrospective measures of information avoidance and information use, which may be subject to recall bias and post hoc rationalization. Although such measures are common in behavioral finance research, future studies could adopt longitudinal or experimental designs to examine dynamic trust updating and entropy regulation over time. Such approaches would allow researchers to observe how repeated exposure to high-entropy information reshapes investors' internal information structures and coping strategies. In addition, integrating digital trace data—such as portfolio monitoring frequency, news consumption logs, or periods of trading inactivity—with Mindsponge- or GITT-informed models could provide more fine-grained evidence on how information avoidance emerges in real time under crisis conditions.

Second, the analysis is conducted within a single-country context (i.e., China) and focuses on a specific crisis period (i.e., the 2022 market downturn). Institutional arrangements, media ecosystems, and cultural norms surrounding trust and authority may systematically shape how investors interpret and respond to financial information. As a result, the generalizability of the findings to other institutional settings—particularly Western financial markets—should be interpreted with caution. Future research could address this limitation through cross-cultural and cross-market comparisons, which would help determine whether the observed trust–entropy interaction reflects a context-specific phenomenon or a more general cognitive mechanism in financial decision-making.

Third, the study conceptualizes information sources as relatively broad categories. Within each category—especially financial newspapers—there exists substantial heterogeneity in tone, analytical depth, narrative framing, and sensationalism that could not be fully captured in the present design. Future research could disaggregate financial news content along dimensions such as sentiment, interpretive depth, framing style, or update frequency to more precisely identify which informational features contribute most strongly to entropy accumulation and avoidance behavior. Combining systematic content analysis with behavioral or transactional data would be particularly valuable in advancing this line of inquiry.

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